

Interview with Anime Director Hirokazu Hanai

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As we mentioned previously, CoolJapan.es attended the FicZone 2023 event. After several years without Japanese guests at this event—dedicated to promoting pop culture, including anime and video games, and which had previously hosted artists of the calibre of Yoshiyuki Sadamoto and Akira Yamaoka—this edition brought us several pleasant surprises. Not only was Nana Kitade’s attendance announced, but we were also able to interview her; and, as if that were not enough, we had the opportunity to meet in person and interview the professional who concerns us in this article, Hirokazu Hanai.

Hirokazu Hanai is someone who leaves a very positive impression. Despite his extensive career—remarkably varied within a single field, that of Japanese animation, or anime—he remains both humble and curious. He has undertaken virtually every role possible within an animation studio when it comes to creating anime, having worked as an animation frame artist, storyboard artist, inbetweeners, key animator, animation supervisor, animation director, project director, designer, and even producer.

He is always approachable, inquisitive, and eager to take on new challenges. During the event, he asked our colleague about his work as an animation teacher—since Andrés teaches precisely that—offered him valuable advice, expressed his gratitude for our interest in his work, and listened attentively to everything we told him about the importance of anime for audiences in our country.

He drew continuously throughout the event and clearly enjoyed his time with attendees and fellow professionals present at FicZone.

Hanai began his career in animation with series such as *Seikai no Senki* and *DNAngel*, among others, working during those years on storyboards, inbetweening, and key animation across various productions. Shortly afterwards, he was already directing episodes in franchises such as *Mirai Nikki*, *Tantei Kageki Milky Holmes TD*, and *Chain Chronicle: Haecceitas no Hikari*. He has also designed characters for *Kono Aozora ni Yakusoku o: Yōkoso Tsugumi Ryō e*, a project adapting a series into a video game, for which he also served as the main director.

His most widely known recent work is perhaps his role as director of the first season of *Don't Toy with Me, Miss Nagatoro (Ijiranaide, Nagatoro-san, 2021)*, adapted from a web manga that began in 2011 and was later published by Kōdansha.

Interview with Hirokazu Hanai

Cool Japan: What can you tell us about your vocation? Did you always want to be part of the animation world?

Hirokazu Hanai: Yes. As for anime, I wanted to become an artist from secondary school onwards, and that has remained the case ever since.

CJ: You have worked as an animation supervisor, storyboard artist, key animator, inbetweenner, and have also been a producer and a director of both episodes and full anime series. Which role in the industry is the most fulfilling for you professionally?

HH: [Thoughtfully] I don't consider myself a great artist—I don't think I am. I believe I am more the kind of person who has a vision. I think of a director as someone with a vision—of how a work should be. I like to think of it that way. And I believe—though I wouldn't presume to assert it—that one of my strengths is advising people, as well as identifying talent, understanding where individuals might fit, and bringing them together. I think I have that ability: to connect people, or to match one talent with another.

There are, I think, two types of director. One is highly talented, says something, and everyone immediately agrees. The other is someone who enjoys listening to their team, to their colleagues. I believe I am the latter.

CJ: You have worked on manga adaptations such as *Don't Toy with Me, Miss Nagatoro*, as well as anime based on video games like *Rockman.EXE (MegaMan Battle Network)*, and you have also worked on *Pokémon*, *Phantasy Star Online 2: The Animation*, and light novel adaptations such as *Dances with the Dragons*. Which type of work has been the most difficult for you to adapt?

HH: When it comes to adaptation... you need to know the entire story of what you are adapting—every aspect of it. If you are adapting a manga, and it has, for example, six volumes... you simply read those six volumes, and that's it, because all the information is there.

But with a video game or a video game series [smiles]...

You have to play it. There's no other way. Video games require a great deal of time in order to understand their story and all their details. That's what makes them more difficult.

CJ: You have worked on internationally renowned series such as *Air Gear*, *Neon Genesis Evangelion*, *Naruto*, *Fullmetal Alchemist*, *Inuyasha*, and *Rurōni Kenshin*. What has it been like for you to know that you have contributed to projects with such global impact?

HH: Hmm... For me, when working on a well-known work, the most important thing—more than the fact of working on adaptations that later became so famous or influential, or adapting works that were already well known—is having the opportunity to learn from and be influenced by the artists involved, to learn from them.

Promotional image of Gayus, protagonist of *Dances with the Dragons*, a series in which Hanai worked as director under the direction of Hiroshi Nishikiori.

CJ: If you had to name an artist you admire or who has influenced you, either within or outside the world of anime/manga, who would it be?

HH: [Thoughtfully] Within the anime industry, I should mention series that have had a lasting impact over time, such as the work of the veteran Masami Abe, for example, on *Urusei Yatsura* [Abe is an industry professional who has worked on well-known and classic series such as *Calimero*, *Hamtaro*, *Ikki Tousen*, *Tokyo Ghoul*, or the aforementioned *Urusei Yatsura*, better known as *Lum, the Invader Girl*].

I could also tell you about the directing work of Hiroshi Nishikiori [Hanai worked with him, for example, on the well-known *Dances with the Dragons*; he is also a professional who has worked on *Trigun Stampede*, *Outlaw Star*, or *Azumanga Daioh*]. Nishikiori was the chief director of the project and I was the anime director.

I should also mention a series that had a strong impact on me, and which I consider my favourite: *Gunbuster (Toppu o Nerae!)*, directed by Hideaki Anno.

CJ: What project would you have liked to carry out, or would you like to work on in the future?

HH: I would like to continue working on *Nagatoro*... I wasn't available for the second season. It was impossible, as I was already immersed in working on the series *Alice Gear Aegis Expansion*, which was released this year, 2023.

I enjoyed working on the *Nagatoro* adaptation so much that I have already offered to return for a third season! I like the series itself, of course, but what really happens is that I feel a strong affection for the character of Nagatoro, and also for Senpai [Naoto Hachiōji]. I have a strong connection with these characters, and I would like to continue developing them.

CJ: With the rise of 3D and digital 2D animation—which has already been established in Japan for around 20 years—how do you view the use of this kind of technology in the industry?

HH: In my case, I don't really mind whether something is created using entirely traditional methods or with the help of the internet, digital tools, and modern technology. It doesn't matter to me, because what I consider truly important is not so much how something is made, but what the final work is like—the finished product. How it looks when it is broadcast on television or online. What matters most to me is that the image is beautiful and engaging, that it is well made and has the best possible finish.

On this topic, I remember the series *Tower of God* (2020), in which I also took part. There was a situation involving a veteran animator... quite an elderly gentleman.

He was an artist who refused to work with anything other than pencil and other traditional tools. At the same time, there was a very young member of the team who worked entirely digitally—completely digital. I decided to keep both of them on the team, thinking that the quality of the final work would improve by making use of the strengths of each, taking into account what each of them did best.

I believe one has to adapt and make the most of each artist's abilities. I think it is not so much about the tool, but about the talent to use that tool.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Hirokazu Hanai for his time, his kindness towards us, and the insightful reflections he shared. We also thank Michie Yamaya, who once again acted as interpreter. Our gratitude also goes to the CrossOver organisation team—especially the press coordinators Eladia and Raúl, who had to perform logistical juggling to organise our interviews given the guests' tight schedules—and, of course, to the other members of the press and media outlets who helped us conduct the interview and assisted our colleague with the equipment.

Hirokazu Hanai drawing Hayase Nagatoro from the anime *Ijiranaide, Nagatoro-san* for the FicZone team at the event's photocall.

Sources

- **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] | **Interview interpreted by:** Michie Yamaya
- **Photographs taken by:** CrossOver press team / **Images sourced from:** Crunchyroll, FicZone official X account

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- *Originally published on CoolJapan.es on 6 August, 2023*
—Entrevista al director de anime Hirokazu Hanai—
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*